

Date: 03/16/21 Operator(s): Victor Driver: Dan Start: Riverside, CA
 Project: NCST Brakes Test Route: Local Riverside and UCR CE-CERT ID: Vehicle End: UCR
 Fleet ID: 356179 Destination: UCR CE-CERT

Daily Start Up Procedure	Daily Shut Down Procedure
☒ Check Generator fuel level <u>Gas Gen</u>	☐ Process data
☒ Analyzers, MEL 1 and MEL 2 Off	☐ Store sample media
☒ CVS Off	☐ Lab Shut Down
☐ Open FID and Air inside MEL	☐ CVS off
☐ Close and disconnect FID and Air 6-pack	☐ Analyzers, MEL 1 and MEL 2 Off
☒ Vacuum Pump Off	☐ Close FID and Air inside MEL
☒ Air Compressor Off	☐ Connect and open FID and Air 6-Packs
☒ Main Power Knife Switch Off	☐ Vacuum Pump Off
☒ Disconnect and Store Power Cable in trailer	☐ Air Compressor Off
☒ Generator On <u>Gas Gen</u>	☐ Connect Power Cable
☐ Vacuum Pump On	☐ Turn Off Generator
☐ Air Compressor On	☐ Turn On Main Power Knife Switch
☐ Analyzers, MEL 1 and MEL 2 On, Set Parameters	☐ Analyzers, MEL 1 and MEL 2 On
☐ Lab Warm Up	☐ Leave analyzers in stand by
☐ PM System Leak Check	☐ Refuel Generator Fuel Tank
☐ Two Zero/Spans	☐ Refuel Vehicle
☐ Initial Ambient Test (before starting on-road test)	☐ Lock up MEL
☐ Start On-Road Test	
☐ End On-Road Test	
☐ Final or Post Ambient Test (after on-road test finishes)	

File ID	Start Segment	Start Mileage	Time Wt Green Start Test	Vehicle Time On	End Segment	Vehicle Time Off	HEM Log Wt Yellow End Test	End Mileage	Comm. #
	Initial Ambient	x		x	x	x	x	x	
	Segment 1	<u>257990</u>	<u>9:23:00</u>	<u>09:27:00</u>	Stop 1	<u>09:55:00</u>	<u>1614</u>		<u>①</u>
	Post Ambient	x		x	x	x	x	x	
	Segment 2				CE-CERT				
	Final Post Ambient	x		x	x	x	x	x	

End Location	End Location
Stop 1	Stop 2

Comments:
<u>① GPS connected at 9:48:41 from HEM data file</u>

